

GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING IN HEARING IMPAIRMENT STUDENTS INTEGRATION PROGRAM

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the implementation of guidance and counselling services for the hearing impaired students in the special education program integration (PPKI) hearing impaired in the secondary school. The qualitative case study method was used to obtain data on these aspects. The data was collected by using the interview techniques and all the data were analyzed with the aid of N'Vivo8. The participants consisted of six guidance and counselling teachers, six special education teachers and three hearing impaired students. The study found out that the implementation of guidance and counselling services is still a lack in PPKI hearing impaired. The guidance and counselling teachers were just only doing some individual counselling while group guidance were more frequently performed. The guidance and counselling teachers are still vague in performing these services because they have no clear guidelines from the Ministry of Education. The conclusions of this study have implications in terms of the practice in guidance and counselling in PPKI hearing impaired, the preparation of the guidance and counselling teachers, the Ministry of Education, and needs further study in this field. Guidance and counselling services in schools now need to engage pupils with special educational. Teacher guidance and counselling should be given courses on how to handle special education students.

Keywords: hearing impaired, Guidance and Counselling, special education

Introduction

Guidance and counselling services are fully implemented in secondary schools since the 1980s. According to the Ministry of Education (2011), guidance and counselling services vision to become a leader in creating a therapeutic atmosphere and environment in the school. According to the second principle in the Guidelines Implementation Guidance and counselling Services in Schools (KPM 1984), guidance and counselling is for all students. According to Mizan Adiliah (2001), as well as special education teachers, guidance and counselling teacher (GCT) also have to play an important role in

identifying the problems of students, designing individual therapy or group on each of the students with special needs. However, even today the role of guidance and counselling services are still vague in helping those with special needs.

Guidance and counselling is enrichment services covering all aspects of student personal development by providing opportunities, facilities and experience in line with their capabilities and potential students. Impaired students were not spared in obtaining these services. Given the various problems faced by them, indeed there is a need for them to express feelings in a rational and emotional counselling or assistance.

People are starting to realize the importance of special education in helping to put these people in the proper place. However, it is difficult to fight for their fate as the problem of diverse and covers many aspects. In terms of personal development, students hearing impaired are no less important. Counselling and guidance teachers must have knowledge of how to channel assistance to the hearing impaired students (Milsom 2002). In fact, the school put the student not only typical but also present students with special needs.

Statement of the Problem

Previous studies related implementation guidance and counselling services among students with hearing impaired is extremely low. The lack of studies on hearing impaired students are in terms of quantity and quality (Sebald 2008). According O'Hearn Pollard (2008), studies on mental health and psychological development of those with hearing impaired is extremely limited. However, in a study of guidance and counselling services for pupils with hearing impaired are less.

The study by Abdul Rahim Mohamad (1998) in printed material not issued on hearing impaired students' attitude towards guidance and counselling services is one of the research in our country. He did a survey in quantitative study in special schools with hearing impaired students showed that they have a positive attitude to a low of only 56.25% of guidance and counselling services. According to him, despite the low but positive attitude hearing students to have confidence that the process of counselling can play an important role in helping them deal with the problem.

In Texas Van Reusen Lomas (1999) conducted a study on the implementation of guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired. This study reviewed the number of schools that provide counselling services to hearing impaired students in inclusive program by the specially trained GCT and identify the demographic characteristics and commissioning. In addition, they asked respondents to assess the quality of counselling services provided to students with hearing impaired. The results of this study, they found that all respondents responded that they perform counselling services to students with hearing impaired. However, 34% of respondents are GCT specially trained in counselling for students with hearing impaired among the GCT is made up of people with hearing impaired. Lomas and Van Reusen (1999) concluded that many schools have shown a positive attitude toward exercise counselling among students with hearing impaired.

In the survey Zieziula and Harris (1998) found GCT prioritize time to implement counselling services to students with hearing impaired. In addition, the glossary is also consulting with other related professional students with hearing impaired and also

conducting counselling activities for students with hearing impaired. 50% of the glossary in this study have academic qualifications in counselling and special education hearing impaired. In this study, GCT assess the level of skills and their communication with hearing impaired pupils. 67% of them felt that formal training in the field of special education hearing impaired they have is adequate. 83% GCT of the respondents responded that their communication skills in a rating of "inadequate".

Moore (2006) conducted a literature review found that at higher education institutions there was only one program to train personnel in the field of guidance and counselling in the United States. According to him, the lack of professional individuals who have caused thousands of hearing impaired students in the country do not get service teacher appropriate guidance and counselling. The same thing also expressed by Marshark, Lang, and Albertini (2002) in their study of the lack of services provided by the counselling to students with hearing impaired.

According to Feldman and Gum (2007) individual hearing impaired need mental health services, but not interact with professionals in this field. According to Mejstad, Heiling and Svedin (2009) kids grow up hearing impaired in special circumstances and they need support from various parties. Therefore, guidance and counselling services are important to students with hearing impaired to develop themselves and also led social lives. What can be done by academics and educators is to make more in-depth study may be applicable implementation guidance and counselling services in schools for those with special needs.

The purpose of this study is to review the implementation of guidance and counselling services hearing impaired among students studying in special education programs integrated secondary school. The aim of this study is also to see implementation of guidance and counselling based on the terms of reference listed by the Ministry of Education.

Methodology

On the implementation of guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired is a qualitative case study method involves using an interview method. The case study is an empirical study of inquiry to investigate specific phenomena in real context (Yin, 2003; Creswell 2003). Interview protocol used consisted of open-ended questions for all study participants. In-depth interview methods used to obtain the required information from six of guidance and counselling teachers, six special education teachers and three students with hearing impaired. Determination of the number of study participants was conducted by data saturation (Bowen, 2008) and based on reasonable coverage of the phenomenon under study (Patton 2002). Purposive sampling method was carried out for the hearing impaired pupils from three secondary schools integration program for special education students performing in the state of Selangor, Kelantan and Terengganu. According to Chua (2006), purposive sampling refers to sampling procedure in which a group of subjects that have certain characteristics were selected as study participants.

Results

Findings of the interviews was to answer the question, namely "How can the implementation of guidance and counselling services among students with hearing impaired?". Based on the interviews of all the study participants, GCT is implementing

guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired. Notification than study participants also can be formulated and established several research themes. Interviews based on themes derived from the 3 categories of study participants as in

Table 1.1.

Tema	Guidance and counselling Teachers						Special education teachers						Hearing impaired students		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3
Guidance and counselling services	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
counselling Program	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			
Transmission services	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√				√	√		
Procedure guidance and counselling	√	√	√	√	√	√	√				√			√	
In response to guidance and counselling services	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√

Table 1.1: Information obtained from all study participants interview producing kajian. Implementation of guidance and counselling services are for all students in the school, in which he also mentioned in the book *Guiding the Implementation Guidance and counselling Services in Schools* (MOE 1984). Through the study found that the glossary will not only provide guidance and counselling services to students in the mainstream but also to students with hearing impaired. The findings are also supported by BOGOR Salim (2005) of guidance and counselling services are services that must be available for all levels of citizens. In the study Milsom (2002), he found that counselling teachers also implement guidance and counselling services to all by Individuals With Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) of 1997 which states schools must provide equal educational opportunities to all students including those with special needs.

GCT in this study did identify a role in implementing guidance and counselling services to hearing impaired students. However, they still left the GCT states in the implementation of guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired. Actually, they did not obtain clear guidelines on the matter from the Ministry of Education (Noraini Rusnani; Abdul Kadir Ismail, 2010).

Although no clear guidelines, GCT still have to provide services to students with hearing impaired in schools based on the concept of "Education for All" (Milsom 2002). While special education teachers in this study provide information that many GCT implementing guidance and counselling service with typical students than students with hearing impaired. The findings Santos de Barona and Barona (2006) also stated that same thing, namely counsellors provide services to all students, including students in special schools, but counsellors more time for the mainstream.

Interviews with six GCT found that guidance and counselling services are conducted among students with hearing impaired. However, all GCT in this study represent either individual counselling or group of students performed less impaired.

This finding is consistent with studies Marshark et al. (2002) and Studer and Quigney (2003) also noted that counselling teachers about providing counselling services to students with hearing impaired. Similarly, findings from Myers (2005) who find guidance counsellor handles many large groups and individual counselling is conducted only when there is need. While GCT less running individual and group counselling sessions with students with hearing impaired but they serve as a guidance. GCT should not only ensure that all students acquire the activities of guidance, but also gained experience individual counselling or group counselling while they are in school (Rusnani Abdul Kadir et al. 2008).

Based on the guidelines guidance and counselling services recommended by the Ministry of Education, GCT should implement programs or activities related to academic, career, psychosocial and mental well-being, parenting, self-development and drug prevention education / smoking / HIV. Interviews show that many control GCT related academic program (eg technical talks answered examination questions) development programs (eg motivation), other than that they control some areas of psychosocial and educational programs of prevention (for example invite the police to anti-crime program). GCT in the study did not specify them to run the program in the field of career and parenthood. Special education teacher also expressed concern that no GCT do program to hearing impaired students and career and parenting program.

Therefore, the results show that the implementation of the program or activity guidance and counselling services for students with hearing impaired do not cover all the areas suggested by the Ministry of Education. The findings of Myers (2005) differs from the findings of which he finds counsellors implement guidance and counselling services for students with special needs as recommended by the American School Counsellor Association (ASCA School Counsellor Association-America). While, the implementation of the counselling program did not cover all the areas listed by the Ministry of Education. However, as noted by GCTSM in this study that they take the initiative to implement a program of guidance and counselling as well as assistance from special education teachers. Myers (2005) found GCT facing challenges and there is no clarity in the implementation of counselling services to students with special needs, but they take the initiative to learn about these students in order to provide continuous service.

The results of this study to obtain feedback that the implementation of guidance and counselling services for pupils with hearing impaired are less either in terms of counselling or counselling program. Different findings in the study Zieziula and Harris (1998), which he expressed counselling teachers spend a lot of time to carry out the counselling session, followed the activities of consulting and coordinating activities for students with hearing impaired. While other studies also reveal GCT provides individual and group counselling or counselling with a focus on the academic aspects, direction, career, interpersonal skills, and consulting parents (Milsom 2002; Scarborough (Milsom 2002; Scarborough & Gilbride 2006; Studer & Quigney 2003).

Guidance and counselling services deployment are also important in implementing guidance and counselling services. The results show that the GCT interviews are conducted scattering guidance and counselling services among students with hearing impaired. However, not all students acquire the information. According to the interview again, only a fraction of the knowledge of guidance and counselling services in schools. Where, GCT do a lot of counselling the distribution of information is done through announcements during the gathering and distributing brochures. According See Ching Mey (2005), have conducted an effective campaign, including distribution of posters, pamphlets, brochures, came out to talk with students, talk about the disclosure of counselling services. Distribution of guidance and counselling services can be done by means of directly or indirectly, so students can understand it clearly and so can have a positive impact (Mohd. Fadzil Jamaluddin, 2003).

Until this study GCT still do not have a specific procedure for the hearing impaired students get their services. Hearing impaired students can get guidance and counselling services similar to regular students. While special education teachers also said they are not aware of procedures for referring cases to GCT students. However, special education teachers said they often make reference case orally to the glossary.

Most counselling to students with hearing impaired are less common. counselling students with hearing impaired do after referred by special education teachers. Impaired students rarely come to see glossary. Counselling sessions conducted is limited. In other words, the amount of exercise counselling to students with hearing impaired are less. Zuria study Mahmud and Ahmad Jazimin Jusoh (2008) found GCT schools in our country have never run individual and group counselling sessions. counselling services are not provided by GCT to students with hearing impaired (Marshark et al., 2002; Nichter). In the implementation of guidance and counselling services, counselors need to assess or measure the effectiveness of the activity or the west after the counselling session (Santos de Barona. Although teacher guidance counselling and state of implementation of these counselling sessions have communication barriers, but at the end of the counselling session impaired students responded that they can express their concerns, get comfortable, have self-awareness and ultimately discussions towards the solution of problems. GCT get more active role in conducting counselling sessions particularly special interaction with students (Livneh, Wilson & Pullo 2004).

Refers to the group counselling sessions also shows that they are poorly executed. Green and Keys (2001) and Stephens, and Jain Kim (2010) states that the group counselling sessions can provide better results than individual counselling. Johnson and Johnson (2004) and Livneh et al. (2004) also claimed this was because teachers counselling can help students with hearing impaired through group counselling to learn to adapt to group members who face similar problems.

There are various views on counselling Program implemented by GCT. There are study participants stating that the counselling program as a motivational talk no impact on the attitudes and achievements of pupils with hearing impaired, but they show the seriousness in the early stages only. Susan Monshie, Rusnani Asmah Abdul Kadir and Ismail (2005) states that motivate a large group only help students grow in self-concept does not apply even academic improvement.

In this study there were also study participants stating that hearing impaired students give a positive response after motivational talks academically conscious student.

However, there are also participants in the study consisted of a special education teacher states that the counselling program as Technical Talks Responding to Lower Secondary Assessment (PMR) is not suitable for students with hearing impaired due to the input given by the speaker is too focused on high academic level that causes students hearing impaired do not understand. The formula is not all counselling programs implemented pursuant to students with hearing impaired. As noted by special education teachers as study participants, speakers or GCT need to know the level and background of pupils with hearing impaired before implementing the program for them. Hosie, Patterson and Hollingsworth (1989) also indicate the same thing: GCT need to know some appropriate services for students with special needs, such as self-reliance skills, the transition from school to the world of careers and higher education tutu way. While Boutin (2008) recommend GCT hold an orientation program because through this program students with hearing impaired may relate to indirect senior students can help them in terms of physical preparation, social, and academic.

Discussion

Implementations counselling services to hearing impaired students in this study showed still not widespread. GCT do less counselling services provided mainly individual and group counselling sessions involves students with hearing impaired. However, instead of programs for students with hearing impaired do not affect all areas listed by the Ministry of Education. While there are some programs that are not appropriate to the level of hearing impaired students. Therefore, GCT advised to carry inventory and records of student services. Services to provide and manage inventory in guidance and counselling is important to help students recognize their potential problematic as a whole and also to determine the direction of their future. In addition, the glossary need to assess each guidance and counselling services in place to obtain feedback and improve their services. In this improvement, collaboration between teachers and guidance counselling, special education teachers and parents of students is required. Dissemination of guidance and counselling services are also important in the implementation of guidance and counselling particularly among hearing impaired students problematic and difficult to communicate with teacher guidance and counselling. Therefore, efforts to spread guidance and counselling services must be improved so that all students know the function of impaired GCT and easily accessible.

This study found that the policy also plays a major role in the implementation of guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired. The Ministry of Education needs to establish clear guidelines to GCTSM in the implementation of guidance and counselling services. As in America, the American Counsellor Association (ASCA - American School Counsellor Association) has listed the areas of special duty to GCTSM working with students with special needs.

The study looked at the implementation of guidance and counselling services among students with hearing impaired or even instead of studying the process of counselling sessions undertaken. Based on the limitations in this study, the researchers gave appropriate recommendations for further research. This study is a qualitative study that examines the implementation of guidance and counselling services to hearing impaired students in the state of Selangor, Kelantan and Terengganu only. Therefore, further studies should attempt to combine qualitative and quantitative methods to make findings can be generalized. After knowing the lack of implementation of guidance and counselling services to students with hearing impaired, the study recommended further

study on the challenges in implementing this service. Further research could also be carried out in connection with an appropriate therapeutic counselling for students with hearing impaired.

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